

Accessibility and Evaluation of Information Sources Skills for Academic Activities by Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria

*¹ADAMU, Abbas Lamido Gora (CLN) (abbasadamu@mau.edu.ng; +2348032095914).

²Professor DAWHA, E. M. K. (CLN) (emmanueldawha@gmail.com; +2348131592268).

³Dr JOSEPH, Damaris (CLN) (damarisjoseph@mau.edu.ng; +2348036251400).

⁴Dr. MAMZA, Wavi Pur (CLN) (mamzaone@gmail.com; +2348139643604).

^{1,3,4}*Department of Library and Information Science, Modibbo Adama University, Yola.*

²*Department of Library and Information Science, University of Maiduguri, Borno State.*

*¹*Corresponding Author.*

Abstract

The study investigated accessibility and evaluation of information sources skills for academic activities by postgraduate students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria. The study was guided by two objectives, two research questions and two null hypotheses. This study adopted a quantitative approach using a descriptive correlational survey and the population of the study comprised of seven thousand eight hundred and sixty four (7,864) postgraduate students registered in 2024/2025 session in three (3) selected federal universities in North East, Nigeria. The universities were: Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University (ATBU), Bauchi, Bauchi State, Modibbo Adama University (MAU), Yola, Adamawa State and University of Maiduguri (UNIMAID), Borno State. Two standardised questionnaire with 5-point Likert's scale were adapted and used as the research instrument. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to analyse data generated from the eight (2) research questions raised, while, regression analysis was used to test the two null-hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that the postgraduate students in North East Nigeria possessed high level of skills in accessing information sources for academic activities. Also, the study indicated that postgraduate students in North East Nigeria possessed moderate level of skills evaluating information sources for academic activities. Furthermore, the hypothesis tested showed that there is significant relationship between accessibility of information sources skills and academic activities of Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria. Moreover, the study reported that there is significant relationship between evaluation of information sources skills and academic activities of Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria. The study recommended sustaining high competence in accessing information sources as well as strengthening information evaluation skills.

Keywords: Accessibility, Evaluation, Information Sources, Skills, Academic Activities, Postgraduate Students, Federal Universities, North East, Nigeria.

Introduction

The 21st century has ushered in new paradigm in all aspects of human endeavour ranging from education, health, governance, manufacturing, banking, business, trade among others which has transformed the society from the hitherto uncivilised to civilised, traditional to modern and from

manual to digital. The society has been proliferated with the development and use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) as well as integration of information that were hitherto accessed through traditional means such as books, journals, conference proceedings, dictionaries and other information resources to digital technologies and electronic information resources such as e-books, e-journals, CD-ROM databases, online databases, Internet, e-zines, e-theses/dissertations, among others, which are the direct consequence of the ICT revolution. This development has indeed posed challenges to how information is accessed and evaluated. The access to information sources of students in universities refers to the extent to which students are able to identify, reach, obtain, and use relevant information resources required for academic learning, research, and scholarly communication. It encompasses not only the physical or digital availability of information resources but also students' awareness, skills, and institutional support that enable effective access (Ibrahim & Sakiyo, 2021). In the university context, access to information sources is a critical prerequisite for effective information seeking, knowledge construction, and academic success.

Evaluation of information on the other hand, refers to students' ability to critically assess information sources to determine their quality, credibility, relevance, accuracy, authority, timeliness, and bias before using them for academic purposes. In the university context, this competence is a core element of information literacy and is essential for effective learning, research, and scholarly communication. At its core, information evaluation enables students to move beyond mere information retrieval to critical engagement with information. University students are exposed to a wide range of information sources—textbooks, scholarly journals, databases, institutional repositories, government publications, websites, and social media. The evaluation process helps them distinguish between scholarly and non-scholarly sources, identify peer-reviewed research, and recognise misinformation, disinformation, or low-quality content (Ibrahim & Sakiyo, 2021). Within university education, the evaluation of information is closely linked to critical thinking skills, academic integrity, and ethical information use. Students who can effectively evaluate information are better positioned to avoid plagiarism, construct well-supported arguments, and contribute meaningfully to academic discourse.

Despite the significance of accessibility and evaluation skills, Popoola (2021) reported that many postgraduate students in Nigerian universities experienced difficulties accessing electronic journals and databases, despite their availability in university libraries. The study attributed these challenges to inadequate training and limited exposure to information retrieval tools. In another study, Ukachi (2023) found a significant relationship between students' information literacy levels and their ability to access, utilise and evaluate electronic resources. However, the study revealed that evaluation skills were weaker than basic access skills. These studies as well as many others consulted by the researcher covered Southern Nigeria or other parts of Northern Nigeria, none focused on North East and most of the studies focused on undergraduate students, hence this study covered North East Nigeria, with a focus on postgraduate students. This is the gap that this study intended to cover to investigate accessibility and evaluation of information sources skills for academic activities by postgraduate students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria.

Statement of Problem

The advent of information and communication technology (ICT) has revolutionised all aspects of human endeavour including access and evaluation of current, reliable and relevant information that could lead to academic success. Postgraduate students are expected to function not only as consumers of information but also producers of new knowledge. This shift has placed strong demands on possessing the abilities to access information and evaluation techniques for effective and efficient academic engagement. Preliminary investigation conducted by the researcher revealed that, investments have been made in procuring information resources, ICT infrastructure, digital libraries and online academic resources with the ultimate aim of supporting teaching, learning and research activities. However, variation still exists in students' access to relevant information as well as competence towards evaluating information sources for academic activities. These challenges as well as others hinder the students from leveraging the huge information resources at their disposal towards academic engagements. Igbo (2020) revealed that students have low e-resources utilisation due to poor digital competencies as they cannot use technology to access information nor use databases to retrieve and evaluate information for solving problems academically. Consequently, the challenges could lead to low academic performance, low quality research while writing thesis or dissertation, huge spending to get access to current information and time wasting which could ultimately prolong their programme, cause disharmony between them and their lecturers especially their supervisors. These and other factors formed the basis upon which this study was conducted to investigate accessibility and evaluation of information sources skills for academic activities by postgraduate students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to investigate accessibility and evaluation of information sources skills for academic activities by postgraduate students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria. The specific objectives were to determine the:

- i. Level of accessibility of information sources skills for academic activities by Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria.
- ii. Extent of evaluation of information sources skills for academic activities by Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. What is the level of accessibility of information sources skills for academic activities by Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria?
- ii. What is the extent of evaluation of information sources skills for academic activities by Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following null-hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance in the course of this study:

- Ho₁:** There is no significant relationship between accessibility of information sources skills and academic activities of Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria.
- Ho₂:** There is no significant relationship between evaluation of information sources skills and academic activities of Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

The access to information sources of students in universities refers to the extent to which students are able to identify, reach, obtain, and use relevant information resources required for academic learning, research, and scholarly communication. It encompasses not only the physical or digital availability of information resources but also students' awareness, skills, and institutional support that enable effective access (Ibrahim & Sakiyo, 2021). Empirically, Oni, Ajagu, Tagwai, Madu and Iwundu (2023) indicated that Information literacy skill programme attended by the postgraduate students of University of Nigeria, Nsukka had instilled in them the ability to identify information sources in their study area, to select and use a wide range of information sources suitable for their study from the library. It had also enabled them to easily plan and search for information using retrieval tools like OPAC, index and abstract. Ndagi and Madu (2023) revealed that lecturers in universities in North Central Nigeria possessed high level of Information literacy in all cases of seven important literacy skills, that is identification of needed information resources, evaluation of relevant information resources as well as access to information resources online database among others. Fasola and Oso (2021) revealed that Postgraduate Students of Ajayi Crowther University, Oyo felt that it was not easy for them to plan and search for information at the library using retrieval tools such as OPAC, index, abstract etc. This may be unconnected to issues of awareness; the library may not have given needed attention to creating awareness on the availability of Online Public Access Catalogue and other retrieval tools. Akinade and Ogunyade (2024) established a significant relationship between information access skills and academic performance among postgraduate students in Nigerian universities.

The evaluation of information refers to students' ability to critically assess information sources to determine their quality, credibility, relevance, accuracy, authority, timeliness, and bias before using them for academic purposes. In the university context, this competence is a core element of information literacy and is essential for effective learning, research, and scholarly communication. Gross and Latham (2022) reported that university students often overestimate their information evaluation skills, demonstrating competence in basic source selection but difficulty in assessing authority, bias, and methodological quality. Similarly, Head and Eisenberg (2020) found that while postgraduate students frequently use scholarly sources, they struggle with deeper evaluation of information credibility and relevance. Fajonyomi, Bukar and Ambali (2021) indicated that majority of students agree that they had a high level of Information literacy especially with emphasis on "evaluation" with a high mean score which showed that the respondents had a high level of evaluation. Odede (2023) found that the respondents were information literate as they showed a considerable ability in identifying, searching, evaluating and using information resources to meet their information needs. Julien and Barker (2024) found a positive relationship between

students' evaluative competence and the quality of academic output, emphasising the role of critical information evaluation in academic success.

Research Methodology

This study adopted a quantitative approach using a descriptive correlational survey investigate accessibility and evaluation of information sources skills for academic activities by postgraduate students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria. The population for the study comprised of seven thousand eight hundred and sixty four (7,864) postgraduate students registered in 2024/2025 session in three (3) selected federal universities in North East, Nigeria. The universities were: Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University (ATBU), Bauchi, Bauchi State, Modibbo Adama University (MAU), Yola, Adamawa State and University of Maiduguri (UNIMAID), Borno State. Research Advisors (2006) published table in which confidence level of 95% with the margin error of ±2.5 was used to select 365 respondents which represented the sample for the study. Multistage sampling is a sampling method that divides the population into groups (or clusters) for conducting research. The study adapted research instrument developed by Society for College, National and University Libraries (SCONUL) (2015) and Digital Competence Framework 2.1 of EU Science Hub (DIGCOMP) (2018). The instrument was validated and pilot test was conducted at Federal University, Minna, Niger State with a total average of 0.85 reliability coefficient. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to analyse data generated from the eight (2) research questions raised, while, regression analysis was used to test the two null-hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Three hundred and sixty-five (365) copies of the questionnaire were administered on postgraduate students in three universities selected in North Eastern Nigeria, out of which, two hundred and ninety-seven (297) (81.7%) copies were properly filled, retrieved and found useable.

Research Question One: What is the level of accessibility of information sources skills for academic activities by Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria?

Table 1: A mean and standard deviation on the level of accessibility of information sources skills for academic activities by Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria.

Table with 6 columns: S/N, Items, N, Mean, Std., Dec. and 5 rows of data.

6	I have the ability to use information to make academic decisions	297	3.81	0.74	HL
7	I can use a range of information technology applications in carrying out an assignment	297	4.45	0.64	VH L
8	I possess the ability to use the information retrieved for academic success	297	4.17	0.67	HL
Cluster Mean		297	3.95	0.70	HL

Source: Field Work (2025)

Table 1 presents the responses on the level of accessibility of information sources skills for academic activities by Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria. In the items listed, the respondents expressed very high level of skills on two (2) items. They include: “the ability to use a range of information technology applications in carrying out an assignment” ($\bar{X} = 4.45, SD = 0.64$) and “the ability to locate quality, current and relevant information” ($\bar{X} = 4.38, SD = 0.66$). The respondents expressed high level of skills on the remaining six (6) items, which include: “the ability to use the information retrieved for academic success” ($\bar{X} = 4.17, SD = 0.67$), “the ability to apply information for research and any assignment” ($\bar{X} = 4.11, SD = 0.68$); “the ability to use information to make academic decisions” ($\bar{X} = 3.81, SD = 0.74$); “the capacity of accessing, reading, and downloading materials from online sources” ($\bar{X} = 3.67, SD = 0.74$); “the ability of using appropriate sources especially offline or online regardless of the formats” ($\bar{X} = 3.52, SD = 0.75$) and “the ability to construct complex searches for different forms of resources” ($\bar{X} = 3.49, SD = 0.76$). Meanwhile, the overall weighted mean score of $\bar{X} = 3.95, SD = 0.70$ was obtained, indicating that postgraduate students in North East Nigeria expressed high level of skills in accessing information sources for academic activities. They showed exceptionally very high level in the use of a range of information technology applications as well as locate quality, current and relevant information, for academic success.

This finding concurred with that Oni, Ajagu, Tagwai, Madu and Iwundu (2023) which indicated that Information literacy skill programme attended by the postgraduate students of University of Nigeria, Nsukka had instilled in them the ability to identify information sources in their study area, to select and use a wide range of information sources suitable for their study from the library. It had also enabled them to easily plan and search for information using retrieval tools like OPAC, index and abstract. Furthermore, Ndagi and Madu (2023) revealed that lecturers in universities in North Central Nigeria possessed high level of Information literacy in all cases of seven important literacy skills, that is identification of needed information resources, evaluation of relevant information resources as well as access to information resources online database among others. However, Fasola and Oso (2021) contradicted this finding and revealed that Postgraduate Students of Ajayi Crowther University, Oyo felt that it was not easy for them to plan and search for information at the library using retrieval tools such as OPAC, index, abstract etc.

Research Question Two: What is the extent of evaluation of information sources skills for academic activities by Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria?

Table 2: A mean and standard deviation of the extent of evaluation of information sources skills for academic activities by Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria.

Table with 6 columns: S/N, Items, N, Mean, Std., Dec. It lists 8 items related to information source evaluation skills, including mean scores and decision levels (HL, ML, LL).

Source: Field Work (2025)

Table 2 presents the responses on the extent of evaluation of information sources skills for academic activities by Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria. In the items listed, the respondents expressed high level of skills on three (3) items. They include: “the ability to separate the good information from the bad information by applying evaluation strategies” (X̄ = 3.75, SD = 0.54); “the ability to distinguish between different information sources and the information they provide” (X̄ = 3.57, SD = 0.57) and “the ability to select the right information from the variety of information retrieved” (X̄ = 3.41, SD = 0.59). The respondents further expressed moderate level of skills on three (3) items listed, which include: “the ability to judge database sources and their relevance” (X̄ = 3.05, SD = 0.61); “the ability to critically appraise and evaluate findings” (X̄ = 2.77, SD = 0.69) and “the ability to appraise each information sources from different components” X̄ = 2.65, SD = 0.70. Similarly, the respondents expressed low level of skills on the remaining two (2) items listed which include: “the ability of reading and analysing information with suitable arguments” X̄ = 2.39, SD = 0.72 and “the ability to assess the quality, reliability, validity, accuracy, authority, currency, relevance, bias, reputation and credibility of the information resources found” X̄ = 2.09, SD = 0.76. Moreover, the overall

weighted mean score of $\bar{X} = 2.96$, $SD = 0.65$ was obtained, indicating that postgraduate students in North East Nigeria possessed moderate level of skills evaluating information sources for academic activities. The moderate level of competence suggests that these skills are not sufficiently advanced, particularly for postgraduate-level academic tasks that require critical appraisal, synthesis, and application of scholarly information.

The finding corroborates several studies such as that of Gross and Latham (2022) who reported that university students often overestimate their information evaluation skills, demonstrating competence in basic source selection but difficulty in assessing authority, bias, and methodological quality. Similarly, Head and Eisenberg (2020) found that while postgraduate students frequently use scholarly sources, they struggle with deeper evaluation of information credibility and relevance. In contrast, Fajonyomi, Bukar and Ambali (2021) indicated that majority of students agree that they had a high level of Information literacy especially with emphasis on “evaluation” with a high mean score which showed that the respondents had a high level of evaluation. Odede (2023) found that postgraduate students of library and information science in Nnamdi Azikiwe University are information literate as they showed a considerable ability in identifying, searching, evaluating and using information resources to meet their information needs.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between accessibility of information sources skills and academic activities of Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria.

Table 3: Relationship between the ability to access information sources skills and academic activities of Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities.

Variable	Mean	Std.	N	R	R ²	Df	F	Sig
Academic Activities of Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities	4.13	0.25	297	.560 ^a	.3136	1	7.701	.004 ^b
Accessibility of information sources skills	3.95	0.70	297					

Source: Field Work (2025)

Table 3 presents the relationship analysis between accessibility of information sources skills and academic activities of Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria. The table shows the observed F-value was 7.701 obtained at 1, 295, degree of freedom (df) with a p-value of 0.004 ($p > 0.05$). The null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between accessibility of information sources skills and academic activities of Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria is therefore rejected. This implies that students who are more skilled at accessing information tend to engage more effectively in academic work and achieve better academic outcomes. In other words, strong access skills such as navigating databases, using IT tools, and identifying credible and up-to-date information are closely associated with academic success among postgraduate students. Akinade and Ogunyade (2024) established a significant relationship between information access skills and academic performance among postgraduate students in Nigerian universities.

H02: There is no significant relationship between evaluation of information sources skills and academic activities of Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria.

Table 4: Relationship between evaluation of information sources skills and academic activities of Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities.

Variable	Mean	Std.	N	R	R ²	Df	F	Sig.
Academic Activities of Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities	4.13	0.25	297			1	1.095	.001 ^b
The Ability to Evaluate Information	2.96	0.65	297	.310 ^a	.0961			

Source: Field Work (2025)

Table 4 presents the relationship between evaluation of information sources skills and academic activities of Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria. The table shows that the observed F-value was 1.095 obtained at 1, 295, degree of freedom (df) with a p-value of 0.001 ($p < 0.05$). The null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between evaluation of information sources skills and academic activities of Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria is therefore rejected. Thus, postgraduate students who demonstrate stronger skills in evaluating information sources tend to engage more effectively in academic activities, although the magnitude of this influence is modest. This suggests that students who are more competent in evaluating information tend to engage more effectively in academic work and demonstrate better academic outcomes. Akinade and Ogunyade (2024) established that postgraduate student with stronger information evaluation skills demonstrated higher research productivity and academic effectiveness. Similarly, Julien and Barker (2024) found a positive relationship between students’ evaluative competence and the quality of academic output, emphasising the role of critical information evaluation in academic success.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study investigated accessibility and evaluation of information sources skills for academic activities by postgraduate students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria. The study revealed that the postgraduate students in North East Nigeria possessed high level of skills in accessing information sources for academic activities. The study also revealed that postgraduate students in North East Nigeria possessed moderate level of skills evaluating information sources for academic activities. The moderate level of competence suggests that these skills are not sufficiently advanced, particularly for postgraduate-level academic tasks that require critical appraisal, synthesis, and application of scholarly information. The moderate ability observed may be attributed to the fact that while students are exposed to large volumes of information through digital platforms, they may lack structured training in critical evaluation criteria, such as assessing methodological rigor, author credibility, publication quality, and research bias. The hypothesis tested showed that there is significant relationship between accessibility of information sources skills and academic activities of Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria. Also, the study reported that there is significant relationship between evaluation of information sources skills and academic activities of Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria. This finding underscores the importance of strengthening information evaluation skills

among postgraduate students. Although students can access and retrieve information effectively, limitations in evaluative ability may affect the depth, credibility, and originality of their academic work. Based on these findings and the conclusion drawn, the following are recommended:

1. **Sustaining High Competence in Accessing Information Sources:** Given the high level of competence and its strong relationship with academic activities, university management should continue investing in electronic library resources, stable internet connectivity, and access to academic databases.
2. **Strengthening Information Evaluation Skills:** In view of the moderate level of information evaluation skills and its significant relationship on academic activities, postgraduate curricula should incorporate critical appraisal of information sources, including peer-review assessment, impact factor awareness, and bias detection.

References

- Akinade, O. J., & Ogunyade, T. O. (2024). Information-seeking behaviour of undergraduate students in Nigerian universities. *International Journal of Library and Information Science*, 12(3), 45–55.
- Babalola, G. A., Adamu, A. L. G. & Afolabi, A. N. (2018). Information literacy: effective tools for equitable and quality education in the 21st century. *A paper presented at the 20th National Conference of Nigerian Association of Library and Information Science Educators (NALISE) held at Benue State University, Makurdi, Benue State between 17th-21st September, 2018; Theme: Information literacy, Sustainable Development Goals and Library and Information Science Education.*
- Fajonyomi, O. J., Bukar, S. S. & Ambali, Z. O. (2021). Information literacy and Use of Library Resources by Postgraduate Students in University of Ilorin. *International Journal of Library and Information Technology (IJLIT)*, 1(1): 66 – 77.
- Fasola, O. S. & Oso, O. O. (2021). An Assessment of Information literacy of Postgraduate Students of Ajayi Crowther University, Oyo. *MBJLIS – Middlebelt Journal of Library and Information Science*, 19: 42 – 56.
- Gross, M., & Latham, D. (2022). What’s skill got to do with it? Information literacy skills and self-views of ability among first-year college students. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 63(3), 574–583. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.21681>.
- Head, A. J., & Eisenberg, M. B. (2020). *Truth be told: How college students evaluate and use information in the digital age*. Project Information Literacy Research Report. University of Washington. Retrieved from <https://projectinfolit.org/pubs/truth-be-told.html>.
- Ibrahim, M., & Sakiyo, J. (2021). Information-seeking behaviour of students in Nigerian universities: A case study. *Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, 6(2), 23–31.
- Igbo, H. U. (2020). Undergraduates’ digital literacy and access to information in Nigerian university libraries: Does Subject background make a difference? *Library Philosophy and Practice*.
- Julien, H., & Barker, S. (2024). How high-school students find and evaluate scientific information: A basis for information literacy skills development. *Library & Information Science Research*, 31(1), 12–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lisr.2008.10.008>.

- Ndagi, S. S. & Madu, E. C. (2023). Effect of Information literacy on use of Electronic Library Resources by Lecturers in Universities in North Central Nigeria. *International Journal of Applied Technologies in Library and Information Management*, 4 (3): 13-22.
- Odede, I. (2023). Information literacy among library and information science postgraduate students of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria. *International Journal of Library Science*,7(2); 32 36.
- Oni, O. A., Ajagu, I. U., Tagwai, A., Madu, B. I. & Iwundu, N. E. (2023). Information literacy among Postgraduate Students of University of Nigeria, Nsukka. *Journal of Applied Information Science and Technology*, 16 (1): 87 – 100.
- Popoola, S. O. (2021). The use of information sources and services and its effect on the research output of social scientists in Nigerian universities. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1–10. Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/183>.
- Ukachi, O. (2023). Correlation of university students' information literacy and their utilisation of library electronic resources in Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Development Using ICT*, 11(3), 45–57.